

Original Research

Drivers, Uncertainties, and Scenarios of the Iranian Economic System

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Abstract

Iran's economy is founded on three main sectors: cooperative, private, and governmental. Various key documents outline objectives for each sector, highlighting certain industries with unique advantages and capacities. These industries not only have strong interconnections with other sectors but also drive demand and contribute to economic growth. This study aims to analyze and present various potential futures for Iran's economy, adopting a holistic and comprehensive perspective. It explores the key factors shaping the economy, including constructive economic drivers, significant uncertainties, and potential future scenarios, considering various influential dimensions. The research employs a qualitative scenario-based approach, structured in eight stages. Data is gathered through interviews, expert panels, and the Delphi survey method, with analysis supported by Mac and Scenario software and a wizard tool. The study identifies primary economic drivers for Iran, including economic growth, oil dependency, the impact of economic sanctions, fundamental challenges, and the level of economic openness. While other factors like high unemployment, a small capital market, rent-seeking, weak infrastructure, and corruption significantly influence the economic landscape, they are not classified as primary drivers in this study. However, these elements will be considered in developing future economic scenarios. Also, in order to prioritize solutions to deal with economic threats, it should be said that using short-term methods in the programs and executive plans of the country's institutions will be the first step to deal with threats. At the same time, planning and using solutions of higher levels, respectively, can move the country step by step in terms of structure and institutions in the direction of resilience, invulnerability and regeneration.

Keywords: Economic Drivers, Future Studies, Iran's Economy, Mac Software, Scenario Writing Wizard.

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Introduction

Economic drivers have the ability to create multiple new economic opportunities based on public opinion, innovation, and technology. As these drivers can create entirely new fields of industry, they play an important role in economic development. In the ideal context, the effect of an economic driver can be particularly effective. The primary effect of economic drivers in the country is economic progress, creating growth and providing more resources to distribute in the community. As production increases, the economy prospers. It is the duty of the monetary policy maker to reduce prices. This is different from inflation in that it applies to times when there is an abundance and variety of goods and services in society. If we look at the past five decades, we can see that economic drivers have evolved. In the 1961's, the Iranian economy experienced rapid growth. First the oil sector, then public services, and finally the industrial sector drove growth, each in its turn becoming the primary contributor to the country's economic growth. The rapid growth of the industrial sector in the 1961's eventually led to it becoming the primary driver of economic growth. By the end of the 1971's, industry, oil, and services, respectively, had become the main engines of economic development.

During the 1991's and 2001's, the contribution of the oil sector decreased such that in the 1991's, industry, real estate, and transportation became the drivers of economic development. By the 2001's, the economy had again evolved until the transportation, industry, and construction sectors contributed the most to economic development. Historical analysis of growth performance shows that the contribution of economic sectors in economic development has changed a lot in the last five decades, with the main contributions at first coming from oil and mineral resources, then industry, and finally the service sector as the years passed. This trend in Iran mirrors the economic development of other countries, where the service sector is emerging as the main driver of economic growth.

In addition to the aforementioned actual contributions of various sectors to economic development, the potential future contributions and roles of economic sectors can also be considered. Certain economic sectors have the potential to be drivers of future economic development due to special advantages and capacities, strong links with other economic sectors, or the potential to create demand for or inputs to other sectors. For example, Chile has been able to activate its mineral capacities and turn the mining sector into a driving force for economic development by creating suitable conditions for mining with extensive investments in transportation infrastructure as well as by removing legal obstacles to foreign investment. In Singapore, the transportation sector plays a primary role in economic development, while Turkey and Malaysia derive considerable income from tourism. In Qatar, the energy sector is the primary driver of growth.

When considering future growth prospects, it is important for Iran to look beyond the historical contribution of the various economic sub-sectors to its development and to identify the potential advantages and capacities of latent economic drivers. Potential growth areas in Iran's economy include transportation, tourism, mining and mineral industries, energy conservation efforts, and knowledge-based services, all of which have the potential to be future drivers of economic development. To this effect, the aim of the

present research is a systematic effort to explain and re-examine the various imagined and probable futures for Iran's economy in a holistic and comprehensive manner. An attempt has been made to identify constructive drivers, influential uncertainties, and finally possible visions of the future of Iran's economy, using an interdisciplinary approach to envision possible scenarios and their various factors affecting this future. It is expected that by considering the key components identified herein and reflecting on the enumerated scenarios, relevant actors will be able to influence the process of building the future.

Literature Review

Continuous and sustainable economic development is an as-yet unrealized dream for a number of countries due to longstanding and widespread policy uncertainties. To ensure sustainable economic development and achieve the ambitious goals of Agenda 2030, it will be necessary to implement a wide range of political initiatives which will promote the sustainable development of a vibrant and inclusive world economy. All economies need facilitating policies supporting the reduction of trade disputes, correct use of energy, utilization of suitable human capital and appropriate foreign direct investment. Therefore, determining the factors of economic development remains the focal point of the efforts of researchers and policy makers throughout the world.

Studies by researchers such as Shahbaz & Rahman, 2010; Omri & Kahouli, 2014; Busse & Koeniger, 2015; Rahman & Mamun, 2016; Rahman et al., 2017; Rahman et al., 2019; have attempted to determine the factors required for robust development, but the results of the studies have been ambiguous. This uncertainty may be due to the heterogeneous nature of the target countries, the use of different methodologies, the variation in data periods, and the lack of selection of appropriate variables. This section will discuss key factors of Iran's economy, including economic structure, economic growth, the effects of economic sanctions, dependence on oil, and the degree of Iran's economic openness.

Economic Structure

Economic structure is defined as the combination of different macro components, the components' relative change over time, and their relationship with income flow (Jackson et al., 1990). Since the advent of oil as a major economic factor, Iran's economy has become a single-product economy dependent on oil revenues, though it has undergone several structural changes in recent years. The past 50 years have seen tumultuous changes to Iran's economic structure. Structural changes began with the implementation of a series of economic and social changes in the 1340's. These, combined with the sudden increase in oil revenues in the 1350's, led to inflation and caused the Iranian economy to suffer from Dutch disease for the first time. The revolution of 1357 and the departure of foreign advisors and investors, mostly American, followed by the war of the 1360's, led to the destruction of infrastructure coupled with a decrease in infrastructure investment. At the same time, increasing population growth in the decades from the 1340's to the 1360's put further stress on the economy. Further structural changes arrived with the economic adjustment policies in the 1370's, and the effort to rebuild after the war resulted in additional changes.

With the large number of structural changes came structural problems. Weak internal management, weak performance of public and private companies, weak economic and educational structure, and poor budget monitoring have all plagued Iran's economy. The excessive growth of liquidity and the resulting inflationary effects thereof, the lack of efficient direction of financial resources toward production and investment, the loss of banks, and an imbalance of pension funds have all contributed to economic weakness as well. There are also further worrisome trends in the economy. A poor business environment and an increase in non-competitiveness and monopolistic behaviors in the production environment have been exacerbated by the economic damage caused by currency fluctuations. Environmental crises such as the reduction of underground water reserves and air pollution have put further stress on the economy. The lack of infrastructure investment has led to a degradation of the capacity of roads, airports, and rail lines, and Iran has been forced to sell raw mineral and petrochemical materials because of a lack of expertise in those areas. Agricultural and industrial equipment is deteriorating because of a lack of equipment. All of these factors result in low efficiency in Iran's overall economy.

Economic Growth

Economic growth is influenced by many factors, including clear improvement in living conditions, comfort of the people of a society, consumption, increased variety in job and lifestyle choices, increased ability to do physically exhausting work, increased efficiency and leisure time, and mastering nature through technological progress. Other factors include the flourishing of talents in various scientific fields, positive and increasing global interdependence, and increased political and military power both within a country and at the international level. Increasing economic growth has long been the focus of individual economists and entire societies (Pajohan & Faghieh Nasiri, 2009; Dezhpasand, 2005). There are different definitions of economic growth. In general, the growth rate of an economic variable is the ratio of the increase in that variable to its initial value. Schumpeter sees growth as slow and gradual changes in long-term economic conditions that result from a gradual increase in the savings rate and population. Kindleberger uses the term "economic growth" only to mean more production. Friedman sees growth as the expansion of the economic system in different directions without changing its foundation. Todaro considers economic growth to be a stable process, as a result of which the production capacity of the economy increases over time and causes an increase in the level of national income. Some economists like Arthur Lewis have used economic growth and development in the same sense. In all the above definitions, economic growth is a quantitative phenomenon of changes in the amount of national production. These changes may be positive or negative. Therefore, economic growth can be both positive and negative. If there is no change in production, economic growth will be zero. Economic growth, in simple terms, is the increase in the production of a country in a particular year compared to its value in the base year. But more important than how to calculate the economic growth rate is to identify the driving forces affecting economic growth. Sally Martin considers correctly determining the drivers of economic growth to be one of the biggest secrets of economics (Pajohan & Faghieh Nasiri, 2009). Economists have identified many factors as effective drivers in increasing or decreasing economic growth. Dezhpasand has identified factors such as human capital and its accumulation, research, physical capital and education as the most important drivers for growth (Dezhpasand,

2005). Molaei and Golkhandan (2014) have introduced government expenditures, including defense expenditures, as negative factors in economic growth. Masoudnia et al, have examined the effects of sanctions on economic growth and have proposed strategies to turn this threat into an opportunity for Iran's economy (Masoudnia et al., 2014). Writers considered human capital important in economic growth and considered it to be effective in economic instability. Also, factors such as education, subsidies, exports, and private sector investment have been considered effective (Kafaei and Jozi, 2013). Pajohan has described the effect of competitiveness (labor, capital and technology) on economic growth as an important driving force. Behbodhi et al has considered many drivers such as human capital, knowledge and technological progress to be effective in growth, but the abundance of natural resources, including oil, without serious attention to human capital has been estimated to have a negative effect (Behboudi et al, 2009). Saif has also studied the vulnerability of the country's currency system in view of the American/Western sanctions against Iran's economy and has proposed solutions to establish a precise currency system, especially economic policies with the aim of diversifying the export of goods and labor productivity, competitiveness and ultimately diversifying foreign exchange sources. (Saif & Khosroshahi, 2013). Mohammadi and Omidvar also discussed the mutual effects of human capital and institutions on the process of economic growth and its influence on Iran's economic growth and has concluded that despite the huge investments in human capital, which are mainly financed by oil revenues, the low quality of the input has caused slow economic growth (Mohammadi & Omidvar, 2015). In his research, Dehghan Shabani considered economic distance (the ease and difficulty of transferring goods, services, labor, capital, information and ideas between the regions of a country) as having a negative effect on the economic growth of a country. (Dehghan Shabani & Akbari, 2015). Ghaffari also studied the relationship between social instability and economic growth and declared that after physical capital and labor force, social instability has the greatest effect on economic growth (Ghaffari et al, 2013). Farajzadeh et al, studied the determinants of economic growth and stated that physical capital plays the biggest role in economic growth, followed by human capital, but social capital and natural resources play a small role in growth. have had economic Iran (Farajzadeh et al, 2017). Ramezanpoor studied globalization (by calculating the indicators of the ratio of exports to GDP, the share of income resulting from the export of manufactured goods, and the ratio of foreign direct investment to GDP) and the employment rate and concluded that in Latin American countries, the correlation between globalization and employment is positive, but in East Asian countries, the correlation coefficient is mostly negative (Ramezanpoor, 2005). Also, Rahbar, in explaining the growth model based on foreign trade, he also pointed out the positive relationship between exports and growth (Rahbar, 1997). Mullings, who has done research on the effects of institutional quality and economic globalization on economic growth, has evaluated institutional quality as having a stable and positive effect on economic growth, but he considered the effect of globalization to be significant only in developing countries, not in developed ones (Mullings, 2018).

Economic Sanctions

Nations use economic sanctions to secure their interests by imposing demands on another country. A large country with influence in the world of politics and economics will be able to impose economic and political costs on a smaller country by placing

restrictions on a smaller economy with less influence than itself. This tool can be especially potent if it is used in cooperation with other important economic and political actors. The issue of economic growth takes on a new dimension for a small country which has been embargoed by a larger, stronger country, a situation that is manifest in the case of the sanctions imposed on Iran's economy (Ezzati & Salmani, 2015).

Economic sanctions certainly put a lot of pressure and difficulties on the ordinary citizens of the country in question. Iran is among the countries that have been the target of various unilateral and multilateral sanctions at different times. After the Islamic revolution in 1980, following the capture of the American embassy in Tehran (1979), the President of the United States ordered the imposition of oil sanctions against Iran. With the subsequent oil embargo established in 1995 and 1996 by the D'Amato-Kennedy bill, a series of unilateral and extraterritorial sanctions increased the volume and severity of these sanctions. The sanctions peaked in 2010 and 2012 with the approval of various laws in the US Congress and numerous executive orders by the presidency of the United States.

Oil economy

Oil is a most important factor of an economy and also essential for the field of science but it is a limited resource. It is a required resource for various phases of manufacturing and production, as well as oil-based products being directly utilized themselves. The fluctuations in cost, manufacturing methods, and its trade often cause a downstream alteration in prices of other goods across the world. It can also lead to an upheaval and begin favoring different entities, depending on how the market leans. When we conceive of raw goods like oil that could be utilized by our descendants, it is important to investigate and comprehend how it will play a role in the future, in terms of economic growth. For example, how will trade of it impact the financial system and those nations that will need to be literally fueled by it for growth and development. There are many unknowns in the process to decipher this.

It is the opinion of Charnavoki & Dolado (2014) that macroeconomic variables are greatly dependent on changes in oil value. Oil accounts for 10% of world trade as opposed to 3-4% for wheat and thereby it demonstrates how it generates money for certain nations. (Zoughi, 2014). As we examine the upheaval in oil prices on the macroeconomics of the United States, we observe that a spike in oil prices has much more devastating effect than the converse positive impact that a drop-in price presents. (Ann et al., 2014) Correspondingly, the changes in the cost of oil on markets and economic growth, demonstrates that business establishments in oil exporting nations that are more prepared, create greater steadiness and balance. (Jarrett et al, 2019) Oil value also has favorable impact on world stock market shares. (Sakaki, 2019).

Persian Gulf nations' reliance on oil is a worldwide illustration of the economic impact of oil. And the increases in oil prices have led to better lifestyles for their citizens. Researchers have opined that higher crude oil prices will help sustain these lifestyles. (Chen, 2016) Macroeconomic markers can all be jolted for a country like Iran, due to its habituation to oil based income. (Manzoor & Taghipour, 2015) Research, mapping the effect of oil market fluctuations on the the value of stocks at the Iranian Stock Exchange,

shows that demand for oil, influences profits at the Tehran Stock Exchange. (Shahbazi et al, 2013) Conversely, the oil price uncertainly index has an adverse impact on GDP growth and that is related to loss of production due to Iran's dependence on oil revenue (Fattahi et al, 2014) .Also, trends such as US policy, Russian energy diplomacy, the growth of China and India, the fragility of the Middle East and North Africa, the solidarity and cohesion of the European Union, the global supply and demand of oil, have a great impact on the future of crude oil prices (Rahbar et al, 2018). Statistical analysis demonstrates that the national budget of Iran is extremely oil dependent. There are instances where the percentage of budget from oil revenue itself is 82% and that makes apparent, the level of dependence. Prior to 2011, it was 12% and subsequently became lower. The amount in the national budget in 2000 was 79% and then it slowly decreased, achieving its lowest amount of 43.3% in 2004, for the period between 2000 to 2010. After 2005, there was greater dependence on oil revenue. Eventually, the national budget's reliance on oil touched 69.6% in 2006 (Allahdini Hesaroeh et al, 2016).

Level of open economy

The verbiage “open economy” is generally applied where there are no obstacles for trade and to the devices and applications needed for industry. This is where the economy has fluid trade and both business and non-business relations with foreign entities. This scenario provides all with an unhindered opportunity to create business liaisons with people and companies from other countries. Foreign trade and private sector investment are emphasized, when utilizing the open economy approach. A nation applying this approach would accept both foreign trade and exchange of the devices and applications needed for industry like money, labor and technology. As long it is competitive in the world economy, this could be beneficial to nations with limited domestic markets.

Clearly, for this reason and to compete on a global scale, a nation must work to create better quality output, while reducing overhead expenditure.

Methodology

This study depends upon a qualitative approach to quantitative research and generally to the scenario-oriented writing process. Here, a plain scenario-based planning model (expert model) has been applied. This research includes mixed methodology in scenario writing with a combination of quantitative techniques including: questionnaires for the analysis of cross-sectional works, Mic Mac software and Scenario Wizard software. This is used in combination with the qualitative techniques of expert panels and interviews. Data collection strategy used here entails investigating sources and documents and doing an environmental survey (interview, expert panel and Delphi survey). Using the snowball method, this is how experts were chosen for interviews, experts' panels and Delphi survey. Consequently, a sample was picked by qualitative and selective method, with 20 people. The experts identified were those with knowledge and specialization in economic areas and also with on hand experience. Distinguishing the catalysts and obtaining the main factors was the objective of the interview. The results from Delphi input data of the used quantitative software were applied to Mic Mac and Scenario software's. Predicated on the result of Mic Mac, the associations among main components were analyzed for

effectiveness and influence and finally possible scenarios were derived using Scenario Wizard.

Findings

Recognizing main findings

Once the data was collected from sources, documents and interviews and interpreted, the research found 26 out of 55 main findings, that would shape Iran's economy. The first round of Delphi survey maintained 26 main findings of the panel. A questionnaire measuring level of importance and uncertainty was also included. This is displayed in Table 1.

Table 1. The importance and uncertainty of the principal parts of the future of Iran's economy

Row	Process	Importance/ uncertainty	The degree of importance/ the degree of uncertainty Score rating scale from 1 to 10	Total score (importance score plus uncertainty score)
1	Economic growth	Importance uncertainty	10 8	18
2	Oil dependence	Importance uncertainty	10 7	17
3	Effects of economic sanctions	Importance uncertainty	9 9	18
4	Uncontrolled inflation	Importance uncertainty	10 4	14
5	Coronavirus outbreak	Importance uncertainty	6 7	13
6	Unsafe investment	Importance uncertainty	6 8	14
7	Steep unemployment rate	Importance uncertainty	8 7	15
8	Constant budget deficit	Importance uncertainty	8 5	13

Row	Process	Importance/ uncertainty	The degree of importance/ the degree of uncertainty Score rating scale from 1 to 10	Total score (importance score plus uncertainty score)
9	Inequality in income dispersion	Importance uncertainty	9 5	14
10	Bank interest rate	Importance uncertainty	6 5	11
11	Imports	Importance uncertainty	6 3	9
12	Economic corruption	Importance uncertainty	8 4	12
13	Limited investment market	Importance uncertainty	9 6	15
14	National economic	Importance uncertainty	9 5	14
15	Political instability of a region	Importance uncertainty	9 4	13
16	Rents	Importance uncertainty	9 6	15
17	Discharge of subsidies for products	Importance uncertainty	6 5	11
18	lack of independence of the central bank	Importance uncertainty	7 6	13
19	Inadequacies of infrastructure	Importance uncertainty	8 7	15
20	Low production rate	Importance uncertainty	7 3	10
21	Low productivity of industry and agriculture	Importance uncertainty	7 4	11

Row	Process	Importance/ uncertainty	The degree of importance/ the degree of uncertainty Score rating scale from 1 to 10	Total score (importance score plus uncertainty score)
22	The extent of liberalization of the economy	Importance uncertainty	10 7	17
23	Limited industry	Importance uncertainty	6 3	9
24	Structural problems	Importance uncertainty	10 9	19
25	Cultural issues	Importance Uncertainty	6 4	10
26	Neglecting the relative costs of the country	Importance uncertainty	7 5	12

Identifying the main catalysts

Subsequent to determining the main catalysts impacting the economy of the nation in the next phase from the 26 main findings with the help of analysis from experts, the most vital points along with the most doubtful are taken into consideration. The calculations regarding the sum of these two measures become the guideline for picking the defining catalysts. With the agreement of the expert panel, all components whose sum of vital and doubtful points were more than 15 out of 20 points, were named catalysts.

Diagram 2 provides an image of distribution of main factors based on vitality and doubtfulness. Diagram 4 numbers refer to Table 1 definitions. According to this, the catalysts of the Iranian economy are as follows: economic growth, oil dependence, economic sanction impacts, level of open economy and structural challenges. All of the catalysts have two areas of doubtfulness that will be employed scenario analysis. There are also other vital and doubtful areas like high unemployment rate, a downsized capital market, rents and dilapidated infrastructure that were not included as catalysts in this research. Regardless, they also have a significant impact, are part of the comprehensive study and will be used in descriptions of prospective situations.

Figure 1. Catalysts recognizing

Effectiveness analysis (MicMac software)

Once we identified the catalysts from outcome of the questionnaires, dealing with vitality and doubtfulness of main areas in the second step of the Delphi process, the impact of each area on the other was studied through the cross-effect analysis matrix questionnaire. The impact of an area on the course of another is classified using the method of structural analysis. 26*26 matrix with 26 main areas was utilized to determine the status of each in regards to effectiveness, influence and mutual relationships in the system. Mic Mac software was used to compare the structural relationships between main areas. The gathered variables and markers were examined via mutual effects analysis method in MicMac.

Visualizing the impact of variables, the five catalysts identified earlier by the software have high level of influence and effectiveness and are assumed to be two-faceted risk variables in the map on the upper and right side. The connection among variables hinged on expert opinions and cross-effect analysis matrix questionnaire is Mac software are shown in the map of influence and direct influence among key areas, as displayed on Figure 2.

Figure 2. Direct (and indirect) effects of 26 key components

Figure 3. Relationships between key variables/components

Table 2. Determination of five scenarios in terms of key uncertainties of the main drivers

Types of scenarios Uncertainty	Scenario 1: A double- edged sword	Scenario 2: The Lion in the Cage	Scenario 3: Half-built House	Scenario 4: Result-oriented Government	Scenario 5: The Logic of Resistance
Structural problems	Decrease	Increase	Decrease	Decrease	Increase
Effects of economic sanctions	Decrease	Increase	Decrease	Decrease	Increase
The extent of liberalization of the economy	Increase	Increase ^l	Increase	Decrease	Decrease
Economic growth	Increase	Decrease	Decrease	Increase	Decrease
Oil dependence	Increase	Increase ^l	Increase	Decrease ^l	Decrease
Total Impact Score	15	4	22	3	16
Compatibility value	·	·	·	·	0

Discussion

The five drivers identified in this article regarding the future of Iran's economy were identified by the MicMac software and are the basis for scenario space design in the Scenario Wizard software. Since the relationships between them are uncertain and complex, they are referred to as "variable risk" in the context of economic structural analysis. The nature of these variables is unstable because any change in these variables will result in a reaction which causes change in the other indicators. Similarly, certain variables can both influence the system and be influenced by other variables. Such variables include unbridled inflation, unfair distribution of income, economic corruption, the state of the economy, political instability, low production rate, and low productivity of industry and agriculture, all of which exert a high level of influence on the system and are in turn influenced by other factors in the system, albeit at a lower level. These variables are known as "penetrating" or "determining" variables. These determining variables cannot be controlled easily in an economic system, but at the same time they play an important role in the future of the system.

Five additional variables of moderate impact and effectiveness play a role in the economic system. Known as "regulating variables", they are central to the future of Iran's economic system. These variables are investment uncertainty, high unemployment rate, bank interest rates, lack of independence of the central bank, and weakness of infrastructure.

Finally, the system is influenced by "independent variables", influences which have less impact than other key variables. These independent variables are import dependence, underdeveloped industry, and cultural problems.

After determining the components which have an effect on the system and accordingly identifying and explaining the space of the research output scenarios in the section which determines the logic of the scenarios, an attempt has been made to describe each scenario

and narrate the story of each scenario by using the findings of the interviews and summarizing the investigations of the third meeting of the research experts. The descriptive narrative of each scenario has been written based on the discussions and qualitative views of the experts, and the validity of the outputs is measured by referring to the opinions of the experts. In writing these scenarios, an attempt has been made to obtain a systematic analysis of the status of each driver and the key factors related to that driver in the space of each of the calculated scenarios.

Scenario 1: A double-edged sword

Iran's economic problems are largely rooted in its faulty structure, aggravated by the passive posture taken by the government regarding increasing economic problems. Such factors as dependence on oil revenues, Iran's small role in international markets, the unwillingness of the monetary and banking sector to enter into production, and the low share of human capital as a portion of overall societal wealth can have a tremendous impact on the prosperity of the nation, hindering production and economic growth. These issues can be aggravated by a passive government. If the effect of sanctions continues to increase, it can cause irreparable damage to the economy, the effects of which will last for years. Reducing the effect of economic sanctions and addressing the endemic structural deficiencies in the economy can open the doors of foreign markets to the country and reduce the atmosphere of investment uncertainty, increase the flow of capital to the country, and increase foreign investment. The influx of equipment into the country-equipment both industrial and military in nature- can increase the country's economic and military power at the national and international levels. Since a large part of the country's national income is dependent on oil and oil revenues, either directly or indirectly through the production of petrochemicals, a reduction in sanctions will increase the net income of the country and the welfare of society will increase accordingly. Likewise, an increase in economic openness can also lead to a reduction in real exchange rate fluctuations and increase specialization in the production of goods and services, which will in turn increase the efficiency of export-oriented sectors, leading to a reallocation of resources from sectors with lower productivity to sectors with higher productivity. Finally, it will cause an increase in production, leading to further economic growth. This economic growth would increase the satisfaction of the citizens of the country, the economic security bringing with it political security. Further, an economically powerful country is more attractive to the international community, engendering in them a desire to establish more and deeper relations as security is established both inside and outside the nation. Providing the essential needs of society through economic growth creates hope, and the hope will lead to further stability and economic growth.

Scenario 2: The Lion in the Cage

The sensitivity of the economy to economic sanctions goes both ways. An increase in structural problems magnifies the scope of a worsening situation with an increase in economic sanctions. Increasing unemployment, worsening inflation, decreased productivity, and misguided or misdirected government policies regarding structural problems will produce a result which is the opposite of that which was intended, giving fuel to the problems plaguing the country and leading the economy to the abyss of destruction. Increased sanctions would decrease Iran's national income. Just the existence

of sanctions causes a loss of faith in the country, causing investors to fear a loss of capital, resulting in increased investment uncertainty and ultimately capital flight. Foreign investors will be either unable or unwilling to invest and will therefore not entrust their capital to the country.

Since a large part of the country's gross production depends on the sale of oil and oil products, the decrease in the income of various economic sectors due to the increase in sanctions will further increase the country's dependence on the sale of oil while a simultaneous decrease in oil sales and the income derived therefrom will hinder the progress of technology in the production of goods and services in all aspects, including the military.

Budget restrictions will have a negative impact on the development of the country, reducing all of the aforementioned aspects of economic growth and societal disorder. Increasing the degree of economic openness can reduce the spread and speed of the problems to some extent. If the government takes the opportunity to use economic openness to improve the private sector, it can improve conditions in a way which will benefit the economy. According to prevalent economic theories, people who become accustomed to a particular level of well-being usually resist the reduction of well-being. This resistance can lead to the disgruntlement of certain groups in social classes and foment societal tensions. An increase in structural problems and an increase in economic sanctions will therefore lead to a decrease in economic growth, and a commensurate increase in public dissatisfaction with the way the country is being run. This public dissatisfaction can turn into a security threat, increasing the challenges faced by the government in providing essential goods. In addition, a reduction of the health, treatment, and education budget due to the stabilization or increase of the military budget can become a factor of insecurity in Iran. Further, a decrease in revenues will cause weakness in the military due to budget constraints, leading to an inability to address issues of national security, resulting in political, military, and cultural tensions in the international arena.

Scenario 3: Half-built House

If structural problems are incompletely addressed and the government attempts to open the doors of the country to the international economy and reduce sanctions through negotiations, more revenue can be brought into the country by selling more oil, but in this scenario it's still possible to experience a reduction in economic growth caused by other variables which affect the economy, with the decrease in economic growth in each sector of the economy causing a decrease in target growth of the economic development programs of the country. For example, backward technology, weak industrial and agricultural sectors, lack of attention to the added value of products and no improvement in the business of selling raw materials can be significantly detrimental to the country's overall goals.

By reducing the effect of economic sanctions and increasing oil sales, it is expected that the budget from the increase in oil sales will be injected into the construction and development of new buildings instead of increasing the current government budget. By increasing the degree of economic openness and removing international trade restrictions,

the possibility of increasing domestic and foreign investment and the entry of technology into the country exists and the quality of domestic products increases.

Along with reducing the effects of economic sanctions, the abolition of financial and banking restrictions would facilitate the entry and exit of foreign exchange resources and increase the speed of development. Of course, an increase in the income from oil exports would provide grounds for more economic corruption and bribery. Since rent-seeking has an advantage in competition with productive activities, it causes the diversion of rare productive entrepreneurial activities toward non-productive areas where profits are easier. Open foreign trade reduces the benefits of corruption and bribery by reducing problems with the structure of the economy, monopolistic and corrupt structures, excessive liquidity growth, and the effects of inflation while also improving the business environment. Reducing sanctions increases people's hope for the future. Furthermore, bilateral communication with other nations will reduce military threats. Considering the political insecurity in areas surrounding Iran, especially Afghanistan, a reduction in sanctions and the establishment of extensive economic relations will increase national security and reduce the threat of terrorism.

The increase in oil revenues resulting from a reduction of sanctions won't be restricted to social programs. Some revenue will be directed toward an increased budget for military institutions, allowing the import of additional military weapons as well as increased production of weapons within Iran. The increased equipment and capabilities of military organizations will allow the country to more effectively combat both internal and external security threats. While the redirection of funds to the military will bring dissatisfaction to some extent, the reduction of structural economic problems will moderate this dissatisfaction.

Scenario 4: Result-oriented Government

Reducing structural economic problems will result in many benefits to Iran's economy. It will improve productivity and reduce unemployment. It will provide confidence in the future state of the economy. The unfavorable business environment will improve and the low share of human capital in the wealth of society will be reduced. Inflation will be reduced by controlling the excessive growth of liquidity. Removing these roadblocks to growth will allow the country to strengthen its infrastructure and allow the government to manage the country more effectively.

Reducing the effect of economic sanctions will open the doors to additional foreign trade and investment. Foreign investment will in turn increase employment and transfer production technology, strengthening the expansion of financial and international resources. The production technology and additional employment will result in increased productivity, which will have the greatest impact on the performance of Iran's economy due to the existence of limitations in the country's available capital. This investment will make Iran's economic growth sustainable, and further, increased productivity in industry will allow Iran to reduce its dependence on oil, making it less sensitive to the threats of foreign countries. On the other hand, reducing the degree of economic openness will have the opposite effect, slowing down trade and making it more difficult to attract investors. While a decrease in imports strengthens the current account, it can also result

in the dissatisfaction of the exporting countries. In the international arena, closing a country's doors can delay the advancement of technology, even in the military sector.

Scenario 5: The Logic of Resistance

The increase in structural problems is the most important reason for Iran's lagging in competition in the international arena. Increasing economic sanctions can fuel these structural problems. The decrease in the degree of the economy's openness along with the aforementioned problems leads to a sharp decrease in economic growth. The decrease in economic growth caused by other economic factors exacerbated by the severity of sanctions or brought about by lack of investment and the high uncertainty involved with investment in the country will endanger the welfare of the people. Although reducing dependence on oil can have a positive effect on economic growth, for this to occur it is necessary to first strengthen other economic sectors. If the reduction of dependence on oil is the result solely of sanctions, and if the ground for this change is not supported through a resilient economy, it will potentially result in domestic and international threats to the country. By reducing the dependence of other countries on Iran and increasing the dependence of Iran on other countries to solve its problems, political tension will rise. The spread of poverty in society caused by the above problems will result in protests as people take to the streets.

Conclusion

The problem raised in this research is the result of studying past trends in Iran's economy and identifying key factors affecting its past and future, examining the results of those effects in the past and extrapolating them into the future. Since the future is unknown, resolving this problem requires the use of the futuristic research method. Futuristic research refers to guesses and hypotheses regarding future developments in various fields of science, which act as a guiding light and organize the course of studies and developments within the framework of the guesses made. Future research is actually a type of historical approach, with the difference being that certainty is avoided and future developments are predicted in the form of different scenarios and guesses. Therefore, while identifying the most important factors affecting the future of Iran's economy and the resulting uncertainty with the help of a study of the past trends of Iran's economy, some possible scenarios of the future of Iran's economy are drawn using the most key economic variables along with a measure of their uncertainty.

In this research, five key variables include: economic growth, dependence on oil, the effect of economic sanctions, the degree of openness of the economy, and identifying structural problems. Five potential scenarios are considered, using the metaphors of a double-edged sword, a lion in a cage, a half-built house, a result-oriented government, and the logic of resistance. Possible futures for Iran's economy were interpreted. From this interpretation, it is clear that the economic sanctions facing Iran challenge any possible positive scenario and influence every prediction about the future of the Iranian economy. The structure of the economy cannot be viewed with a clear perspective without the intrusion of the negative effects of the sanctions. The analysis of the sanctions imposed against the Islamic Republic of Iran and the risks they have caused is always accompanied by many complications due to the wide scope of the covered area. It can be

said that in terms of macroeconomic criteria, sanctions that affected financial and monetary transactions, infrastructural and knowledge-based industries, oil, gas, and petrochemicals of Iran have the most negative consequences. Therefore, denying the effects of sanctions on the macro economy is not considered a suitable solution for Iran's economic development. On the other hand, the structural weaknesses of Iran's economy have a less-negative effect than that of sanctions. Even if sanctions did not exist, or if they were lifted by the countries which imposed them, Iran's economic system has fundamental structural challenges that make economic development difficult and require detailed multilateral planning. Structural problems such as excessive growth of liquidity and the resulting inflationary effects thereof, the lack of efficient direction of financial resources toward production and investment, the loss of banks, the unfavorable state of balance sheets and the freezing of bank resources, the imbalance of pension funds, and debt accumulation are all trending in a worrying direction.

Likewise, the increasing lack of budgetary resources to compensate for shortcomings such as currency fluctuations, inappropriate business environment and non-competitive atmosphere and monopolies in the production sector, the limited volume and diversity of the country's foreign trade compared to gross domestic output and the existence of monopolies and corrupt structures bode ill for the country's economic prognosis.

Based on the findings of this research as well as the future scenarios of Iran's economy, it is necessary that policymakers, especially the governance system, should pay serious attention to the expansion of international interactions, exports resulting from the conversion of raw resources into added value, and management components in the economy. In addition, the policies of increasing the share of new energies, environmental considerations, innovation and technology development should be considered at all expert and managerial levels due to their high impact on the future of crude oil. Also, in order to prioritize solutions to deal with economic threats, it should be said that using short-term methods in the programs and executive plans of the country's institutions will be the first step to deal with threats. At the same time, planning and using solutions of higher levels, respectively, can move the country step by step in terms of structure and institutions in the direction of resilience, invulnerability and regeneration.

On the other hand, people who consider globalization as a threat to Iran's economy, their unspoken default definition is that Iran's economy has no strong points that can be presented in the world arena, and this is an incorrect and incorrect thinking. Iran's economy can be effective on the world stage by relying on the knowledge and creative power of the country's young society and the vast human resources and underground resources and diverse geographical conditions and use this opportunity to introduce and identify the country and its potential capabilities and powers.

It is suggested for future research; 1- In addition to focusing on the threats in scenario writing, the opportunities facing Iran's economy should be discussed. 2- Foundation data method can be used in modeling possible scenarios. 3- In order to remove the threats to Iran's economy, short-term, medium-term and long-term solutions should be provided.

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